

Measuring the Electron – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework that regard the electron as the Majestic (3) and the nature of the primordial coupling constants series and Variational manifolds, it is possible to provide new insight about the problematic issue of measuring a particle as the electron.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

Electrons in this framework are represented by the majestic (3). Since it is not an even number it cannot vanish into matter. Since it is trapped on the bracket it can't propagate like the net variation $N_V = \gamma$, which are net curvature on the matric tensor or ripples. The conclusion is that the electron is propagating across the nuclei, the hadron structure which is two and three divisible to vanish into matter. Now in physics there is the problem of measuring the energy of the electron, and the problem is due the varying the radius, the smaller the radius the higher energy of the electron. So at radius aspiring zero, infinite energy is manifested, against observations.

One would like to add certain notes on the issue on measurement. First, regarding the electron as a separate entity is wrong. The electron is part of the manifold, and is effected by what is going on the matric tensor. Trying to measure it solely based on radii seems to relay on too simplistic ideas, which ignore complexity. Second, measurement of the electron in a varying radii will take a certain period of time. For all this period we will need to know where the electron is which is impossible to do. So measurement of the electron propagating across the nuclei seems to be impossible to do, as modern physics regard the electron as a cloud of probability.

Third, suppose it was possible to measure the electron for a certain period of time. the measurement is done via scattering photons onto the electron and by doing so varying its energy, increasing it. Of course, the electron can omit those photons to a new direction or in a different rate, but measuring the electron will affect the electron energy and so the experiment itself is part of the problem.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5$$

$$(3) + 5 = 8$$

$$8 = 0$$

The thing to take from this short assay is that the problem of measurement is not just due to radii leading to an infinite energy scales, as $r \rightarrow 0$ but also due to the time needed to perform the measurement and the influence of photons as a tool of measurement that clearly effect the measured object by varying its energy, as it get absorbed into it. Another possible problem is the existence of the measurer that is matter on the manifold. The configuration of matter on the manifold is varying the matric tensor and causing it to accelerate outward and the manifold is different due to the matter configuration, given by the main equation of the 8T.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)